

Discourse Analysis in Language Education: Implications for English Language Training and Learning: An Overview

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Article Information

Suggested Citation:

Ghafar, Z.N.. (2023). Discourse Analysis in Language Education: Implications for English Language Training and Learning: An Overview. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(3), 65-72.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).07)

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Abstract:

The background of discourse analysis (DA), as well as its significance and applications in different educational contexts, will all be covered in this paper. Additionally, it describes how English language training could benefit from DA factors to improve the standard of language education. The findings of this research are consistent with the notion that language acquisition or instruction cannot occur in a quiet environment. Immersion in real-world and social contexts is essential for effective language learning and teaching because it enables learners' goal of acquiring a language to effectively use their freshly caught information and skills for good conversation. This research aims to improve both language instruction and learning methods and outcomes. It addresses numerous uses of speech analysis in language classes. Additionally, the investigator identifies

the biggest obstacles to successfully putting this plan into action and analyzes them, offering specific suggestions about how to do so. This study is predicated on the idea that students who emphasize applying their language skills to social and cultural situations would talk effectively and confidently.

Keywords: *discourse analysis, instruction in language, interaction, applications social aspects, sociolinguistics, language acquisition, instructional methods.*

Introduction

The ability to communicate with different populations is a fundamental aspect of implementing any language. People largely rely on language and the grammatical diversity they already possess to convey these signs, making it simpler for people to comprehend one another in everyday interactions and to exchange ideas and information. The conversation and interaction that takes place inside a classroom environment between students and teachers is an essential component of successful second language acquisition. These elements are

significant because of the role they play in providing a context for the educational experiences of students (Domalewska, 2015). As a result, language may be seen as the primary means of communication between members of various cultures worldwide. Language may be seen as a tool for promoting global understanding since it is utilized to translate many nations' cultural traditions and values. Sirbu, A. (2015). In other words, languages may be considered the primary tool for efficient communication (Philomina, 2015).

Discourse analysis is a legitimate method for examining written and spoken language that has emerged due to the communicative approach's focus on actual communicative actions in language learning and instruction (Chambers, 2007).

Additionally, during the last several decades, there has been a significant movement away from emphasizing the phrase and its constituent parts to emphasizing the context in which language is employed. Additionally, this opens the door for "Discourse Analysis" to develop. Numerous studies have been conducted to learn more about the new approach's characteristics, methodologies, and range of potential applications in various sectors as a consequence of this new approach's communicative nature's ability to capture researchers' interest (Drid, 2010). Many areas where language plays a crucial role in human communication, like discourse analysis, originate in language.

On the other hand, discourse analysis may be seen as a broad field of study that includes linguistic analysis of speech by illuminating the language's structure, functions, and distinctive linguistic features (Rashidi & Rafieerad, 2010). Form and function play a role in discourse. It is possible to rely on these two viewpoints to demonstrate how language is employed in social interaction. The significance of these characteristics and features comes from the study for academics is made easier by translators' understanding of them. Dialogue, discourse people, starting and ending discourse, turn-taking, selecting the next speaker, duplication, subject bargaining, speech mistakes, fixed methods, conversation instigation, and role-playing can all be used to symbolize these characteristics and qualities (Osoba, & Sobola, 2014). Tabrizi et al. (2014) claimed that discourse analysts employ communication as the major language medium to transmit information in various sectors to represent the nature and relevance of communicative aims. Discourse analysis, including photos, songs, and videos, may be used in any setting or circumstance (Martínez, 2012). Discourse analysis helps speakers comprehend and interpret underlying reasons in paper or verbal conversations

(Berrocal et al., 2016). Discourse is multifaceted. Investigating these processes' creation requires. Discourse Analysis has examined the link between linguistic Form and function in spoken and written texts, particularly considering that oral and recorded discussions have different societal purposes and communication functions (Tabrizi et al., 2014). DA studies how individuals use language to accomplish social objectives, focusing on cultural ideologies in conversation. Thus, discourse analysis may be employed structurally to analyze text organization and ethnographically to understand cultural processes (Wennerstrom, 2003). According to Osoba et al. (2014), Language analysis programs concentrate on the patterns and organization that characterize human language.

Information and Various Components of the Instrument

This study shows how important discourse analysis is to language learning. Language instruction involves communication. Phonology, morphology, syntax, and others are worthless without social context. Thus, the interaction between language interpretation and social context may assist learners in quickly acquiring meaning via speech practice. Observing and recording L2 learners' performance may help the study's purpose. This method is good for learning more about a subject since it addresses social factors that impact human performance. The researcher monitoring L2 performance collects and interprets the data. In the Synthesis course offered by the researchers at the Kurdistan College of Languages, students at the L2 level study the vocabulary and morphology of the English language over a year. The primary purpose is to make strides in sociolinguistics and language comprehension. Using language in diverse social situations, such as asking for favors, inviting others, giving and accepting praise, apologizing, etc. L2 students should focus on how "situational variables such as the cultural backdrop and the speech's circumstances affect their decision of what should be said" (Brown, 2000). The researcher examined L2 learners'

performance data to see whether discourse analysis exercise improved communication, fear, and self-confidence. Politeness, formality, culture, and other sociolinguistic competencies will be studied (Brown, 2000). Assessing body language, gestures, and eye contact. L2 learners need context and culture to understand social linguistics communication codes (Bennett, 1998). According to this research, L2 students will have higher levels of language competence and self-assurance than students who completed comparable classes without incorporating linguistic material into contexts of society and culture.

The Meaning of the Term Discourse Analysis

The various discourse analysis readings can be ranked in the following manner when the theory's context is taken into account:

According to Fairclough (1995), discourse analysis is the study of various texts within the context of the sociocultural activity. According to this analysis, "attention to textual form, structure, and organization at all levels is required, including phonological, grammatical, lexical (vocabulary), and higher levels of textual organization in terms of exchange mechanisms (the allocation of talking turns), constructions of contention, and universal (activity sort) structures" (Fairclough, 1995, p. 7).

Some academics have attempted to define discourse analysis by relating it to the statement. Discourse analysis is described as "the systematic study of naturally occurring (not imaginary) interaction in the broadest sense, at the level of interpretation (rather than merely material acts or characteristics)" by Bavelas, Kenwood, and Phillips (2000, p. 102).

Additionally, Gee (2011) offered a description of discourse analysis comparable to the previously mentioned ones: "The research on linguistic use. It would be more accurate to say that it is an investigation of language in use rather than just a method of communication.

Mit'ib, M. A. (2010) defines discourse analysis as a "methodological tool that lends itself easily to investigating the fundamental characteristics of

speech, the developmental process, and discrimination by identifying social views and concepts accountable for noticed language patterns" (Mit'ib, 2010, p. 39).

Discourse analysis and the language being used have been connected by Rashidi and Rafieerad (2010). They define it as "the study of language usage by people who make up a speech community. It examines verbal interaction as well as written materials, taking into account both language structure and functions. It highlights linguistic traits that distinguish different kinds of writing and cultural and social factors that help us perceive and comprehend various texts and styles of conversation (Rashidi & Rafieerad, 2010, p. 95).

According to Jiang (2012), discourse analysis studies the link between communication and its environment by illuminating linguistic structure and function, spoken interaction, and written texts. Discourse analysis is described as "identifying language characteristics that characterize various genres as well as social and cultural factors that facilitate our comprehension and interpretation of various texts and types of talk" in this definition (Jiang, 2012, p. 2146).

The Importance of Analyzing Discourse in the Field of Language Education

The communicative approach to language teaching, which first appeared in the early 1970s, is regarded as an important turning point in the history of language teaching. This is likely due to its ability to raise awareness of the importance of focusing on communicative language features, which paved the way for developing "language for communication" and "language as communication."

In order to provide students with actual chances to experience and execute communication, language teaching's goal is to help students communicate, even in constrained situations, using the target language. Here, discourse evaluation has become a crucial element in language instruction using the communicative method (Olshtain & Celce-Murcia, 2001).

Discourse analysis examines how native and non-native speakers use language in the social

environment to help language learning by focusing on language shapes and roles in social interactions. In other words, discourse analysis focuses on the specific language features that individuals employ to communicate social meaning utilizing language's grammar, syntax, pronunciation, and phonology (Berrocal et al., 2016). There is a growing consensus that the academic field of discourse analysis is crucial to both the instruction and acquisition of foreign languages. They are essential in helping people communicate with one another. While practicality deals with the meaning inferred from language processing and social interaction, discourse analysis focuses on the intended purpose and sequential connections imparted within context. To put it another way, one might argue that for the language teaching procedure to be in line with discourse analysis, it strongly emphasizes interpretive and facilitative communication tactics for learners (Olshtain & Celce-Murcia, 2001).

According to research by Danesh, Aghagolzadeh, and Maftoon (2016), students' reading comprehension improved after learning about critical discourse evaluation and its components because they were more motivated and efficient learners. In other words, one may claim that a critical approach to teaching EFL is represented by fundamental discourse analysis. It helps students improve their command of the English language. Discourse analysts are interested in understanding the connection between the various linguistic units to arrive at an in-depth structure of meaning. For instance, they may examine the grammatical structures of utterances to comprehend and analyze the ideas conveyed in speech. For instance, in addition to gathering information, the enquiring Form may communicate goals, make requests, and give suggestions (Hai, 2004).

Discussion and Forward-Looking Suggestions

The student's degree of connectedness and participation is increased, and the gap between their theoretical comprehension of language and actual language use is closed, all due to the

introduction of sociolinguistic material and the explication of grammatical standards. For instance, the teacher asked the students to develop terms that complement individuals in various social and cultural contexts. This was a portion of the instructor's explanation to L2 students of the abstract construction of adjective sentences. It has also been looked at from a different cultural perspective to demonstrate appreciation and how commendation recipients feel about it. The same is true for other abstract language structures, such as showing contrition and admitting responsibility for wrongs done to other people. Students need to comprehend that saying "I'm sorry" is not just a method to apologize for harming someone from the perspective of society. They need to understand that saying "I'm sorry" is a way to say "I'm sorry." For example, even when there isn't anything wrong, people in England are always quick to apologize. They frequently express regret, regardless of whether they are repeating what others have said, inquiring about something, or interrupting other presenters. Participants in the study have been exposed to various social and cultural contexts while refining their abstract verbal proficiency in the language that will be the focus of the study. According to the researcher, exposing students to real-world scenarios has improved their communication ability, made them feel better about themselves, and significantly reduced their nervousness while exercising their language skills in class.

The Implementation of Discourse Analysis into the Learning Environment

Discourse analysis in educational settings is a well-known example of the direct application of sociolinguistic theory to instructors' daily work. The use of discourse analysis in the classroom fosters the development of meta-discursive thought in both students and instructors, an essential component of multilingual education at the level of current international educational systems. In addition, discourse analysis is thought to be the most effective way to comprehend the shifting repertoires within the educational setting (Rymes, 2010).

The complex relationship between student and instructor interactions and how this relationship influences the actual learning that takes place in the classroom can be better understood by applying a methodology known as discourse analysis (Woodward-Kron & Remedios, 2007). Effective instruction needs to make use of discourse analysis in the educational setting. It allows us to determine how much leeway instructors should be given to use the expression in the classroom (Qomi, 2019). In addition, it supplies us with vital information regarding the study of languages and how this study impacts our understanding of culture (Martinez, 2012). In the classroom, discourse analysis is utilized to assist instructors and students in better comprehending the various situations and determining how language operates in each setting (Rymes, 2008). The expression "critical classroom discourse analysis" references the transformation of "classroom discourse analysis" into "critical" when classroom academics analyze the effect of their works on the classroom and the phrase "classroom discourse analysis" itself (Rymes, 2008). According to Rymes (2010), a novice discourse analyst who wishes to carry out discourse studies in an educational setting should adhere to the following steps:

- (1) Spend some time making a list of all the opportunities for public speaking in the classroom. Please find the most important event or any relevant occurrences that are similar to it.
- (2) Write down the main event and describe the language used. You won't need to transcribe the lecture to complete this. Start with listening to the audio, then note the discussion that distinguishes this event using the categories mentioned as a guide. For instance, pay attention to how names and nicknames are used, the implications of multilingualism, greetings, brand names, expressions of admiration, and politeness. Define the linguistic norms that apply to this occurrence. Write down the conversational passages that use this characterization the most.
- (3) Examine the interconnected occurrences for linguistic distinctions. As Griffin did, they

investigated one "disruptive" student. You could follow Philips' lead and explore how different students behave at various points in the day (pp. 542-543). Texts that contain grammatical locations where rules can be addressed are given a greater emphasis on discourse-oriented grammar. To make sound decisions given the circumstances, students must have a solid grasp of grammatical conventions and instruction in speaking and context.

Discourse plays a significant part in lexicon learning and teaching because words cannot be taught separately from their settings, so they must reflect the meaning substance. Discourse-oriented reading, as outlined by Olshtain and Celce-Murcia (2001), allows students to interact with literature by involving them in selecting the reading material. This fosters pupils' growth as independent learners. According to Dar, Rahimi, and Shams (2010), 99% of students reported feeling more motivated and intrigued to study the works after understanding the critical discourse analysis.

Several factors are about the instructors, pupils, and the learning atmosphere in a school setting. It is not easy. Sociologists, academics, translators, and psychiatrists have examined it because of its complexity. Another popular subject in classroom study and second language learning is classroom talk, which looks at how instructors and students communicate and how they can develop their speech skills. It depicts how teachers and pupils share during a normal class (Qomi, 2019).

The interactive approach has also been used in teaching languages for particular goals due to developments in discourse analysis study in the latter half of the 20th century (Chambers, 2007).

Discourse analysis is a powerful instrument that teachers can use in the classroom to support students in creating new identities in the quickly globalizing world of today. Teachers can use discourse analysis to encourage social interactions in the school. Discourse analysis may be considered a technique for changing classroom practice when the traditional duties of teachers and pupils have altered to suit their new positions in classroom discourse. Discourse

analysis may be incorporated into teacher education classes to help students understand their new responsibilities regarding discourse analysis skills and talents (Rumenapp, 2016).

Discourse analysis offers methods for acquiring linguistic expertise in situations where English is not the native tongue and is, therefore, not regularly utilized in social interactions at the level of instruction and study of English as a foreign language. It enables the use of questions that are thought important for linguistic growth and makes it easier to comprehend how English is used socially outside of its own country to improve communication between languages (Escobar et al., 2015).

The following are some suggestions made by Berrocal et al. (2015) for instructing students to utilize spoken discourse more successfully in the classroom:

- Providing natural language in basic or informal settings helps students understand and become conscious of the discursive habits connected with a certain context or circumstance. This helps learners reflect on discourse and communication.
- Make use of activities involving self-recording.: The first stage in teaching discourse analysis consciousness is implementing more real-world tasks that call for self-recording activities. Include practices that allow students to capture and write down their own unplanned words for later study to help them become more communicatively competent. This aids the students in developing self-monitoring awareness. Use exercises that can readily be altered to fit various foreign language education circumstances that match the course functions.
- Collaborative analysis: Encourage pupils to examine their own and other people's verbal exchanges. Developing their interview questions and conducting peer interviews is essential for students. They should always record themselves so that the precise words they use to ask inquiries and provide answers are preserved. They may then record their talk after that. In the data analysis, learners will find it easier to identify

words, phonemes, or grammatical aspects with the aid of a transcript.

- Request from the students to divide the objective language into ability areas like grammar, spelling, and articulation. Analyze various elements for each location. Finding common characteristics in conversations may be done by paying particular attention to the nouns, verbs, and adjectives.
- Promote examination of spoken conversation, especially casual talk's many facets: Learners will be given various chances to participate in discourse via interactive activities encouraging engagement. Language professors will likely observe that students' speech patterns vary depending on the communicative task. For instance, arguments and spontaneous role plays might be instances of these jobs.
- Teaching culture requires discourse analysis: Language and culture are inseparable. Students will understand intertextuality's role in the argument by studying a culture's language usage. English as a second language students developing their communicative competence in a foreign culture may benefit from this analysis because they can compare and contrast the environment they are learning in and the culture they are trying to learn.
- Use media to examine speakers realistically: Analysis of media technologies is common in critical discourse. Discourse and social interaction captured on audio and video are realistic and sincere both within and outside the classroom. English instructors may assess a short speech or conversation and compare verb tenses and vocabulary using traditional British and American English videos.

Components of Analyzing Different Types of Discourse in the Classroom

In the classroom, discourse analysis looks at how teachers can guide the learning setting while fostering learning groups (Otten, 2010). A group with a common geographic place and similar information, culture, values, and dialects can be called a discourse community. In light of this depiction, viewing the language classroom as a

unique discourse group in which teachers and pupils share several interests seems possible. The pledges and obligations that each group member must keep are also outlined in an unwritten "contract" that exists. Olshtain & Celce-Murcia (2001). Describe language education as a forum for discourse where students and teachers can develop their language and cultural discourse skills. Following are the factors for speech analysis that Rymes (2016) has outlined:

- Social proper context, which includes a person's complete biographical experience, determines the repertory that a person may command. Spanish is probably a substantial component of my conversational toolkit if I was raised in Iraq. Considering that social environment also influences how people perceive and use of. Even if a student chooses to use Kurdish in English class, a teacher may have regulations prohibiting using any other language, such as English.
- The context of an encounter (how it develops from moment to moment) affects which aspects of a person's repertoire are shown and how they work. If I speak Kurdish, for instance, whether someone decides to answer in English or Kurdish (or in another language, for that matter) might influence the direction of our discourse, even if there are no formal restrictions regarding which languages are acceptable in our chat.

Conclusion

Communication and interaction in the classroom, whether between students themselves or between students and the teacher, are essential to successfully developing a second language. The conversational strategy gives rise to discourse analysis, rooted in various academic disciplines. The primary objective of discourse analysis is to study the unique relationship between language and the setting in which it is employed. It does this by shedding light on the relationship that exists between the shape of the language and the functions it serves, and the result is a concentration on how languages are used in spoken and written documents. The

analysis of classroom discourse is important to the practice of teaching because it assists us in comprehending the complex interactions that exist between students and instructors and provides knowledge that is helpful in the field of language analysis. Numerous educational institutions have adopted the collaborative method of teaching and learning; however, due to challenges concerning the preparation and training of teachers, the technique has not yet generated the intended outcomes. It is essential to recognize that the processes of teaching and learning that do not use discourse are ineffective because the success of these procedures depends on the methodology they employ and, to a significant extent, on the address they operate within the setting in which they are used.

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